

HIGH INTEREST IN THE BABURIDS DYNASTY IN WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract. *This thesis examines the study of the history of Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur and the representatives of the Baburids dynasty by English and English-speaking Indian writers. At the same time, unique literary works of the writers are listed and brief information about them is provided.*

Key words. *Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, Humayun Mirza, Akbarshah, Shahi Jahan Mirza, Taji Mahal, Alex Rutherford, Ira Mukhoty, Jadunath Sarkar, Uzbekistan, India, Afghanistan.*

Introduction. Our great ancestor Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur Mirza is one of the world figures who has gained fame not only in Uzbek literature, but also in world literary studies. Our research has shown that more than a dozen artistic and scientific works have been created in English literature alone about the life path, creativity, and military activities of Babur Mirza. However, it is interesting that the history of his descendants who later ruled the state founded by Babur in India, in particular his son Humayun Mirza; his grandson Akbar Shah; and the founder of the Taj Mahal, which is now considered a famous architectural monument in India, Shahi Jahan Mirza have not been ignored by world writers. During our research, we were convinced that the unique books of English and English-speaking Indian writers reflect the truths related to the history of the representatives of the Baburids dynasty, who ruled India for more than 3 centuries. In our opinion, it is both surprising and sad that there is so much interest in the history of this dynasty in world literary studies at a time when Uzbek writers have created rare works about Babur Mirza and his descendants. Below, we will get acquainted with some of these novels.

Discussion. First of all, the epic novel “*Empire of the Moghul*” by the English writer Alex Rutherford, consisting of 6 books, takes its place at the top of our list, because this work of art is an invaluable work that tells about the period from the history of Babur Mirza to the overthrow of the Baburids dynasty in India by the British. The components of the epic novel are as follows: “*Raiders from the North*”; “*Brothers at war*”; “*Rulers of the world*”; “*The tainted throne*”; “*The serpent’s tooth*”; “*Traitors in the shadow*”. The noteworthy aspect is that in the process of writing a historical biographical novel, the author of the work relies on not only on

existing sources such as “*Baburnoma*”, “*Humayunoma*”, “*Tarihi Rashidi*” to reveal the real history, but also visits the countries where the events took place, in particular Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, and India, and tries to see with his own eyes the paths traveled by the heroes of his work, and to feel their emotions in his own body, at least once. In our opinion, this makes each book of the epic novel even more impressive and serves to reach into reader's deep heart.

Another English writer, William Dalrymple, also dedicated his work to the descendants of the Mughals, entitled “*The Last Mughal*”. This work describes the reign of the last representative of the Mughals, Bahadur Shah Zafar II, who was on the throne in name only at that time, and the end of the Mughal rule in India by the British military in 1857.

Ira Mukhoti, an English-speaking Indian writer, is also interested in the history of the Mughal empire and has created two great literary works. One of them is the novel “*Akbar: the Great Mughal*”, dedicated to the history of Akbar Shah, the son of Humayun Mirza, who ascended the throne at the age of 13 due to the untimely death of his father and is recognized as one of the greatest rulers in the history of India. Author’s interest in the history of Akbar Shah was not in vain. Akbar Shah was an unrivaled ruler both in the military sphere and in state administration. During her reign, great changes were made in the fields of education, science, culture, art, literature, the living conditions of ordinary people improved, and positive changes were made. The work written by Ira Mukhoty also tells the story of this “Golden Age” in the history of India. The second work written by her is called “*Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire*”. Often, authors write works about the lives of rulers, their military campaigns, and political activities, but Ira Mukhoty sets herself the goal of writing about women and girls from the Mughal dynasty, who actively participated in political processes and were able to influence the rulers, even if they did not have any political power,. This work reveals the history of Khanzada Begum, Babur Mirza’s sister who was able to cross the icy lands of 750 kilometers on horseback at the age of 65; Gulbadan Begum, the author of the work “*Humayunnama*” that provides information about the era of Babur Mirza, Humayun Mirza and Akbar; Mohim Enaga, who supported Akbar Shah in the administration of the state at the age of 13.

Another English-speaking Indian writer, Jadunath Sarkar, published his work “*Fall of the Mughal Empire*” in 1964. As is known from its title, this work also provides information about the history of the overthrow of the Baburids dynasty by the British military.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the Baburids dynasty, due to its significant importance in the history of Asian nations, including India and neighboring countries,

has attracted great interest from world writers of the XX-XXI centuries. In particular, the overthrow of this dynasty by the British government and the conquest of India led English writers to conduct extensive research on the history of the foundation of the Baburids statehood. It would certainly surprise us if English-speaking Indian writers did not write historical, artistic and scientific works about the descendants of Zahiriddin Babur, who ruled in their native land for more than 3 centuries. Although Babur Mirza left his native Andijan as a teenager, he was still a real Uzbek. We look forward to such unique works from our national writers from Uzbekistan. At this point, it is a very sad situation, in our opinion, that we are limited to only the biographical novels and travelogues of our writers such as Pirimqul Qodirov, Khayriddin Sultanov, and Kamchibek Kenja.

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